

Size distribution and elemental analysis of fine particles from Li-ion battery cell fire

Lukáš Preisler^{a,*}, Simona Šachrová^b, Jiří Pospíšil^a, Tomáš Sitek^a, Renata Komendová^b

^a Energy Institute, Brno University of Technology, Brno, Czechia

^b Institute of Chemistry and Technology of Environmental Protection, Brno University of Technology, Brno, Czechia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Particles
Fine particles
Size distribution
Li-ion battery
Thermal runaway
Cascade impactor

ABSTRACT

The rapid rise of lithium-ion batteries, especially in electromobility, raises firefighting challenges due to thermal runaway and the release of hazardous aerosol particles. Understanding their properties is key to assessing environmental and health risks. This study focuses on the analysis of fine particle emissions from fires of cylindrical lithium-ion battery cells of two distinct chemistries, namely NMC and NCA. The primary objective of the analysis is the particle size distribution, elemental composition, and morphology. The cells are subjected to thermal abuse in a sealed testing chamber until thermal runaway occurs. The explosion and fire lead to the release of particles, which are captured using a 14-stage cascade impactor. The range of sizes of the collected fine particles is from 14 nm to 9.7 μm, with the mass mode diameter between 152 nm and 377 nm. Subsequent analysis of each stage filter of the impactor utilizes atomic absorption spectrometry and atomic emission spectrometry to ascertain the elemental composition of the particles. Among the 11 analyzed elements, lithium exhibits the highest concentration in particles smaller than 1 μm, while nickel is predominant in particles larger than 1 μm. Subsequent analysis of particle morphology and elemental composition is facilitated by SEM-EDS.

1. Introduction

Electromobility has emerged as a prominent representative of environmentally friendly transportation in recent years. Electric vehicles (EVs) have high engine efficiency in comparison to internal combustion engines and generate zero tailpipe emissions. Despite the significant potential of electromobility, numerous unresolved issues remain, such as electricity production, the availability of rare materials, and the production of batteries, with the main current focus on lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). The growing demand for EVs highlights the increasing importance of LIB safety. While these batteries enable advanced technology, they also pose significant risks, particularly during thermal runaway (TR) events that can lead to fires or explosions. The fire of LIBs emits elements that are hazardous to human health, including cobalt, aluminum, copper, and lithium. Fine particles released during such incidents present substantial health hazards when inhaled into the lower respiratory tract.

In the event of an accident or malfunction of a battery cell, TR may occur. The initiation mechanisms of TR are electrical, mechanical, or thermal abuse (Liu et al., 2022; Larsson et al., 2014). Electrical damage occurs after overvoltage, overcurrent, overcharge, over-discharge, or

short circuit (Larsson and Mellander, 2014). Thermal initiation of TR occurs after local overheating, or extreme cold (Luo et al., 2022). Overheating can lead to the vaporization of the liquid electrolyte, resulting in the formation of gas (Essl et al., 2021). Damage to the separator can result in the cathode and the anode of a battery cell becoming electrically connected, leading to strong exothermic reactions (Pfrang et al., 2017; Loveridge et al., 2018). The process leading to thermal runaway is generally divided into three distinct phases (Golubkov et al., 2014): Phase I is the initial heating stage, where the cell is heated by an external source while internal structural changes, such as endothermic separator melting, begin to occur. During Phase II, the cell becomes its own heat source due to internal exothermic reactions, causing the temperature to rise until the TR trigger point. Phase III is the final stage, defined by a sharp increase in the heating rate accompanied by massive venting and particle generation. This rapid escalation significantly increases internal pressure and degrades electrolyte stability. A significant amount of heat is generated, causing the temperature of the surface of a battery cell to rise to 400 °C (Zhang et al., 2019a; García et al., 2024). Furthermore, the sparks generated during an explosion may reach temperatures up to 1200 °C (Wang et al., 2020). The intensity of TR is dependent on state of charge (SOC). When a battery cell is fully charged, the reaction is significantly more intense compared

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Lukas.Preisler@vut.cz (L. Preisler).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2026.109134>

Received 10 March 2026; Received in revised form 4 May 2026; Accepted 10 June 2026

Available online 11 June 2026

0957-5820/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of Institution of Chemical Engineers. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Nomenclature	
AAS	atomic absorption spectrometer
AES	atomic emission spectrometry
EDS	energy dispersive spectrometer
EEPS	engine exhaust particle sizer
ELPI	electrical low-pressure impactor
EV	electric vehicle
GMMD	geometric mass mean diameter
HEPA	high efficiency particulate air
ICP-MS	inductively coupled plasma - mass spectrometer
IDLH	Immediately dangerous to life or health
LIB	lithium-ion battery
NCA	lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide
NMC	lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide
PM	particulate matter
SEM	scanning electron microscopy
SOC	state of charge
TR	thermal runaway

The process of TR has the potential to result in the occurrence of fire and explosion, releasing smoke into the atmosphere. The composition of the smoke is a mixture of gaseous and particulate matter, including solid and liquid particles. This particulate matter (PM) contains a mixture of elements and substances, such as heavy metals (Wang et al., 2020). The release of gas can be attributed to three primary mechanisms: electrolyte decomposition, the reaction between anode and electrolyte, or the decomposition of cathode materials (Wang et al., 2020) and binders (Spotnitz and Franklin, 2003; Wang et al., 2023a). A comprehensive analysis of the gaseous toxic substances was conducted by Wang et al. (2020) and Zhang et al. (2019b). The composition of the gaseous emissions primarily consists of CO₂, CO, H₂, H₂O, hydrocarbons, and other substances, depending on the composition of the cathode material. These substances include highly toxic gases such as HF, PF₅, and PO_F₃ (Larsson et al., 2014). Claassen et al. (2024a) found a significant emission of gaseous H₂SO₄ from LCO and LFP battery cells. In addition, Nedjalkov et al. (2016) identified the presence of benzene, toluene, styrene, and biphenyl. TR of a NCA battery cell emits CO and HF at concentrations significantly higher than IDLH (Ubaldi et al., 2023). These emissions may trigger a range of health concerns, including respiratory irritation, asthma attacks, respiratory infections, cardiovascular diseases, pneumonia, persistent cough, respiratory failure, and even death (Valavanidis et al., 2008).

to a battery cell with a low charge (Li et al., 2024a; Essl et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020). Due to the TR of a single battery cell, there is a high risk of fire propagation to other cells (Niu et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2023).

The released stream of aerosols contains approximately 17% by mass of solid particles of various sizes (Zhang et al., 2019a). In a heterogeneous aerosol environment, complex processes of nucleation and

Fig. 1. Scheme of particle processes during TR.

particle growth take place, which are schematically depicted in Fig. 1 as described below. The emission of particles may occur directly into the atmosphere or via firefighter water (Zhang et al., 2019a). It has been observed that nearly 90% of the total particles, including settleable particles, by weight, are smaller than 500 μm (Li et al., 2024b). Particles larger than 100 μm are predominantly formed from the disintegration of the electrodes and the separator. These particles are characterized by a significant settling velocity, resulting in a relatively short persistence in the atmosphere (Alves et al., 2020). When the gas stream carrying particles is directed toward a solid surface, impaction leads to particle deposition on the surface.

Particles smaller than 100 μm create a polydisperse aerosol that rapidly fills the entire volume of the test chamber. The smallest particles, known as ultrafine particles, are typically up to 100 nm in size. These particles are formed as molecular clusters, mainly during the initial phase of vapor condensation (nucleation) (Kulkarni et al., 2011). Ultrafine particles do not sediment. They are carried by airflow (advection) and are subject to intense dispersion due to the turbulent flow (Kulkarni et al., 2011). Molecules in the surrounding medium are in constant Brownian motion, colliding with the particles. Under these conditions, particle movement is influenced by diffusion, which is the primary transport mechanism over short distances for particles smaller than 0.1 μm (Einstein, 1905). These particles possess a higher surface-area-to-volume ratio, which facilitates their inhalation into the respiratory system.

A characteristic behavior of ultrafine particles is their tendency to agglomerate into larger entities by a process called coagulation (García et al., 2024; Barone et al., 2021). The interaction between two particles of smaller size leads to the formation of a larger particle through the interplay of van der Waals adhesive forces and electrostatic forces. The rate of coagulation increases with higher particle number concentrations and higher turbulence intensity in the flow. The process of particle growth is further enhanced by the additional condensation of vapors onto particle surfaces. As the size of the particles increases, gravitational effects become more pronounced, leading to an increase in settling velocity. Changes in ambient relative humidity can alter the moisture content of the particles, affecting their mass and potentially their size (Ahlawat et al., 2020). Additionally, particles may undergo fragmentation processes. This process of fragmentation can be initiated by collisions between larger particles that possess sufficient momentum, due to centrifugal forces during periods of intense rotation, or as a consequence of vibrations (Kulkarni et al., 2011).

Particles smaller than 2.5 μm are among the most hazardous air pollutants due to their ability to reach the acinar region of the lungs, where gas exchange occurs (Kim et al., 2015). As PM can adsorb toxic gases, polycyclic aromatic compounds, and heavy metals, it acts as a carrier of these substances into the body. Exposure, particularly to metal-containing PM, has been linked to carcinogenic, neurological, and kidney-related health issues (Sall et al., 2020). These risks highlight the need to assess the particle size distribution of emissions. The severity of health effects depends on the concentration of respirable particles and the duration of exposure, with both short- and long-term inhalation posing different risks.

A limited number of studies dealt with the size distribution of particles emitted during battery cell fires including the elemental composition of these particles. Zhang et al. (2019b) studied the elemental composition of settleable particles according to their size ranging from 0.85 mm to 8 mm. Li et al. (2024b) sorted particles by four sieves of size between 54 μm and 500 μm with the peak size between 100 μm and 300 μm . It was observed that the majority of the particles did not exhibit a spherical morphology (Li et al., 2024b). Li et al. (2024a) observed a positive correlation between the SOC and nickel content, on the one hand, and the median particle size, on the other. The majority of the experiments were conducted on fully charged battery cells. Mao et al. (2019) demonstrated a correlation between the lithium content in particles and the SOC of a battery cell. Wang et al. (2020) used inductively

coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) for elemental analysis of particles with size below 500 μm to detect Ni, Cu, Zn and Cr. The elements predominantly detected in particles from fires of battery cells with lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) cathodes are carbon, nickel, cobalt, aluminum, lithium, or fluorene (Zhang et al., 2019b). Premnath et al. (2022) measured the size distribution of fine particles following overcharge and nail penetration of NMC battery cells using engine exhaust particle sizer (EEPS). The highest mass of particles emitted was between 20 nm and 100 nm. The study of Claassen et al. (2024a) revealed the peak of mass distribution of LFP battery cell 568 nm and of LCO battery cell 668 nm using electrical low-pressure impactor (ELPI). Both battery cells had 100% SOC and it was shown that lower SOC emits smaller particles. Mass concentration of PM₁ accounts for 81–95% of all PM₁₀ particles (Claassen et al., 2024a).

The morphology of particles from battery cell TR can be categorized into three primary types: fragments of the anode or cathode, microspheres, and nanoparticles (Barone et al., 2021). Microspheres are predominantly composed of nickel, aluminum, carbon, fluorene, and oxygen (Barone et al., 2021). Ubaldi et al. (2023) used Scanning Electron Microscopy and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) to determine the size and composition of particles captured to a PTFE filter. The size of captured particles was $1.54 \pm 0.69 \mu\text{m}$ and they were mainly composed of Li, Ni, Co and Al. Xu et al. (2024) collected particles on a soot collection plate placed 150 mm above NMC and LFP battery cell to determine soot composition by SEM-EDS. Soot from NMC battery cell contains over 50% of carbon followed by fluorene and oxygen with nearly 15%.

Other research in the field includes the study of temperature-related phenomena, such as spark detection, the design of capture systems, and the development of protective equipment against fine particle emissions (Li et al., 2024a). The limited number of studies published on the elemental composition of particles in relation to their size distribution is evident (Zhang et al., 2019a, 2019b; Wang et al., 2023b; Li et al., 2024b). However, the majority of these studies deal with the elemental composition of particles only in non-respirable fraction of particles. The knowledge about the elemental composition of fine particles is lacking. Claassen et al. (2024b) investigated the elemental composition of PM_{2.5} from LFP and LCO battery cell fire exploring, that more than 50% of the particle mass was from carbon. Elemental content of heavy metals such as iron, cobalt, nickel or copper were below 1%. Consequently, the present study aims to address this knowledge gap by focusing on the elemental composition of particles in the respirable fraction of aerosol particles. That corresponds to particle size from 14 nm to 10 μm with the main focus on particles smaller than 1 μm .

2. Methods

2.1. Battery samples

Two variants of standard cylindrical 18650 lithium-ion battery cells were utilized in the experimental setup. The technical characteristics of both battery cell variants are shown in Table 1. The cathode chemistries of the battery cells were NMC for LGDBHG21865 (No. 1) and Lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide (NCA) for Sony Murata US18650VTC5A (No. 2), with the nominal capacity of 3.0 Ah and 2.6 Ah, respectively. These chemistries were selected due to their usage in the current EV market, enabling a comparative analysis of how their distinct thermal

Table 1
Technical characteristics of battery cells.

Battery cell	Chemistry	Nominal voltage (V)	Nominal capacity (Ah)	Mass (g)	Energy density (Wh/kg)
No. 1	NMC	3.6	3.0	45	240
No. 2	NCA	3.6	2.6	47	199

stabilities influence particle formation and emission profiles. The identical manufactured composition of the tested commercial cells provides a uniform chemical baseline. This ensures that observed variations result from the inherent thermal runaway stochasticity, not from manufacturing differences.

The cathodes were extracted from the battery cells and their surface was analyzed using SEM-EDS. The detailed elementary composition of the cathode materials is presented in Table 2. The composition is normalized to the sum of measured elements. Lithium was not measured by EDS but is also a component of the cathode. It is notable that both battery cells exhibit the highest concentrations of nickel and cobalt. The most significant difference in composition is observed in the presence of manganese. The analysis further revealed the presence of zirconium, with concentrations of 1.5% in battery cell No. 1 and 0.8% in battery cell No. 2. This suggests that zirconium was incorporated as a dopant in the form of zirconium oxide. The presence of phosphorus and fluorine indicates the residual electrolyte. Furthermore, Cu and Al current collectors constitute significant mass fractions of the cells and are therefore expected to be prevalent in the particles. All the battery cells utilized in the experimental setup were fully charged. Each battery cell was subjected to a controlled heating process using an external heat source until a TR was triggered. The battery cells were arranged in a vertical orientation, with the safety valve positioned towards the top.

2.2. Experimental setup

The heating of battery cells was conducted within a sealed testing chamber, with a volume of 200 liters and equipped with a pressure valve to prevent significant pressure build-up during the thermal runaway event, see Fig. 2. The battery cell was clamped by a 10 mm thick aluminum heating block attached to its center. The heating element involves a resistance heating with the power of 40 W. The surface temperature of the cell was monitored by a K-type thermocouple. The thermocouple was connected at the center of the vertical section of the battery cell using a steel ring.

The interior of the testing chamber is continuously exposed to outdoor air through a 10 mm diameter opening equipped with a HEPA filter, ensuring the incoming air remains uncontaminated. This connection maintains the interior of the test chamber at atmospheric pressure throughout the experiments. For the homogenous distribution of particles within the volume of the testing chamber, two PC fans are placed in both vertical and horizontal directions to mix the air with the particles inside the test chamber. During the TR event, the gas and the particles leave the battery cell in an upward direction along the longitudinal axis of the battery cell, as shows Fig. 1. Big particles are captured on an impaction inflammable surface to protect the rest of the equipment in the test chamber. Sampling of particles for subsequent analysis is conducted in the upper portion of the test chamber. Inside the test chamber a high-frame-rate camera was placed to determine the length of TR and to capture images of TR phases.

2.3. Experimental design

The first set of experiments was conducted using the cascade impactor Dekati HT-DLPI +. This apparatus utilizes 14 impactor stages with polycarbonate filters to systematically classify particles based on

Table 2
Cathode material of battery cell composition by EDS.

[wt%]	C	O	F	Al	Si	P
No. 1	8,7	1,7	0,2	0,8	0,1	0,2
No. 2	11,9	2,1	0,7	1,6	0,1	0,6
[wt%]	S	Mn	Co	Ni	Sr	Zr
No. 1	0	4,4	11,2	70,9	0,4	1,5
No. 2	0,2	0	12,6	69,5	0	0,8

their aerodynamic diameter via inertial impaction. The filters have diameter 25 mm and a pore size of 0.4 μm . During this process, particles with sufficient inertia deviate from the gas streamlines and deposit onto the corresponding filters. The range of captured particles is from 14 nm to 9.7 μm . The size range of the particles trapped on the individual impactor stages is given in Table 3. The filters with captured particles were weighed to determine the mass size distribution of each fraction. Subsequently, the filters with particles were submitted for elemental analysis.

In the second set of experiments, a single filter from polycarbonate with a diameter of 37 mm and a pore size of 0.4 μm was utilized for particle capture. This filter demonstrates the capacity to capture a broad spectrum of fine particles. The increased quantity of captured particles provides a more comprehensive perspective for subsequent elemental analysis. The experimental procedure is shown in Fig. 2. The testing chamber inner air with particles is pumped through a cartridge containing the filter. The third set of experiments used a cascade impactor again to capture the fine particles on aluminum foils with a diameter of 25 mm. Subsequent to this, the particles were subjected to a thorough examination via SEM to ascertain their morphology.

The filters with captured particles from tests 1 – 4 were subjected to elemental analysis to detect hazardous elements. Analysis was first made for blank polycarbonate filter. Its composition was subsequently subtracted from the analyzed value. The analysis of metal content in the samples followed a structured procedure that began with placing each sample filter in a teflon container. Then, a mixture of 9 ml of hydrochloric acid (HCl) and 3 ml of nitric acid (HNO₃), known as aqua regia, was added to the Teflon container. The samples were then subjected to microwave digestion, a process that ensured complete dissolution of the metals. Following this step, the samples were transferred to plastic tubes and stored in a cool, dark place to maintain stability. Na and Li concentrations were measured using a PFP7 Jenway flame photometer based on atomic emission spectrometry (AES). For the analysis of other metals (Al, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, and Pb), an atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS) (ContrAA 800) with electrothermal atomization was used. Samples were diluted according to the estimated concentration of each element and injected into the spectrometer using an autosampler with 20 μl of sample and 5 μl of matrix modifier (Mg(NO₃)₂ or Pd/Mg(NO₃)₂). To ensure the accuracy and reproducibility of the measurements, three replicates of each sample were obtained.

Table 4 summarizes carried out tests and corresponding analysis used for identification of particle size distribution and elemental composition. A total of six separate TR events tests were carried out.

The study uses varied sampling parameters rather than identical statistical repetitions. Because the measurement uncertainty of our analytical instruments is negligible compared to the inherent variability of TR as an uncontrolled safety event, variations in total collected mass are an anticipated outcome.

3. Results and discussion

Visual documentation of the TR process is presented in Fig. 3, illustrating its distinct evolutionary phases. The left image shows phase II (the venting phase) and was captured after the gas release through a pressure valve few seconds before the jet flames appeared. The middle image captures the violent eruption of phase III and is the most exothermic part of TR. The image on the right shows the cooling period of phase III the heat release of particles which were deposited on a surface above the battery cell. The red flames are indicative of lithium combustion. From the video capture, the duration of phase III was quantified, with TR lasting 2.5 s, 24.3 s, 19.3 s, and 35.3 s in Tests 1–4, respectively. These results highlight the large variability in TR time-scales. All measured durations remained well below the total particle sampling interval.

The surface temperature profiles of the battery cells clearly marked the initiation of Phase III immediately prior to the rapid thermal spike.

Fig. 2. Setup of the experimental methods including particle capture and further analysis.

Table 3

The theoretical size range of the particles trapped on the 14 individual floors of the impactor.

Stage	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Min size [nm]	-	14.7	30.6	55.2	94.1	152	252
Max size [nm]	14.7	30.6	55.2	94.1	152	252	377
Stage	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Min size [μm]	0.377	0.596	0.938	1.62	2.42	3.62	5.32
Max size [μm]	0.596	0.938	1.62	2.42	3.62	5.32	9.79

Table 4

Composition of the tests performed.

Test No.	Battery cell	Particle collection	Size distribution	Chemical composition
1	No. 1	cascade impactor	gravimetric analysis	AAS, AES
2	No. 2	cascade impactor	gravimetric analysis	AAS, AES
3	No. 1	single filter	-	AAS, AES
4	No. 2	single filter	-	AAS, AES
5	No. 1	cascade impactor	SEM	EDS
6	No. 2	cascade impactor	SEM	EDS

For battery cell No. 1, the initiation temperatures were recorded at 174.5, 169.3, and 164.7 °C for tests 1, 3, and 5, respectively, with corresponding maximum temperatures peaking at 392.4, 389.9, and 467.5 °C. Conversely, battery cell No. 2 exhibited Phase III initiation temperatures of 186.9, 176.0, and 189.0 °C during tests 2, 4, and 6, respectively, subsequently reaching maximum surface temperatures of 432.9, 416.6, and 307.3 °C. The temperature profiles confirm TR stochasticity: stable initiation temperatures contrast with unpredictably fluctuating maximums. This physical randomness drives the variability in total aerosol mass, proving that generalizability lies in the thermodynamic mechanisms, not exact mass totals.

3.1. Particle size distribution

Experiments were conducted on NMC (battery cell No. 1) and NCA

(battery cell No. 2) lithium-ion battery cells. In all cases, particles generated during TR were captured by drawing the contaminated air from the interior of the testing chamber through a tube to the filters. The diameter of the tube is 5 mm, and the length is 50 mm for tests 3, 4, and 300 mm for tests 1, 2, 5, and 6.

During the first set of tests particles from TR were captured by the cascade impactor, followed by gravimetric analysis to derive the size distribution curve of fine particles. The total mass of particles from test 1 was 22.6 mg with a capture time of 3 min and an initial airflow of 10 l/min. Stages 7–12, ranging from 152 nm to 2.42 μm, captured a minimum of 2 mg of particles. The maximum mass of 5.42 mg was captured on stage 8, which contained particles from 252 nm to 377 nm. The particle size distribution obtained from the gravimetric analysis is presented in Fig. 4a. The maximum mass concentration recorded in stage 8 was 1045.0 mg/m³.

Test 2 captured the mass of the particles 14.2 mg during the 1.5 min capture interval at an initial airflow of 10 l/min. At least 1 mg of particles were captured in stages 7–13 ranging from 152 nm to 3.62 μm. The highest mass concentration 940.8 mg/m³ was identified in stage 7 ranging from 152 nm to 252 nm. The particle size distribution is presented in Fig. 4b. The data from test 2 shows a bimodal profile with a secondary peak in stage 11. This bimodal behavior is characteristic of the more aggressive NCA chemistry, where lower thermal stability triggers a more violent eruption and a correspondingly higher release of coarse particles. Stage 2 of the particle size distribution was excluded for both tests 1 and 2, due to the inadequate quantity of collected particles.

The results were compared with other studies in Table 5 using the geometric mass mean diameter (GMMD). However, the limited number of available studies makes direct comparison difficult due to differences in battery chemistries (NMC, LFP, LCO, NCA) and abuse methods (nail penetration, overcharge, heating). Only experiments using battery cells at 100% SOC were included in the table. Therefore, the compilation cannot establish a direct baseline due to various test representations. All experiments reported a mass mean diameter below 1 μm. Thus, hazardous submicron aerosol emission is a universal feature of Li-ion failures, regardless of cell chemistry or abuse mechanism.

In another set of tests particles from TR were captured to a single filter by initial airflow of 15 l/min for a duration of 15 min. The mass of captured particles from test 3 was 28.6 mg. A similar outcome was observed in test 4, with a total mass of 29.9 mg. The particle size analysis reveals a consistent pattern: regardless of the specific battery chemistry, the emitted aerosols are dominated by deeply respirable submicron particles. This highlights a universal inhalation hazard.

Fig. 3. Capture of TR phases: (a) venting phase, (b) violent eruption and (c) cooling of battery cell No.2.

Fig. 4. Size mass distribution of fine particles collected on foils by cascade impactor from (a) battery cell No.1 and (b) battery cell No.2.

Table 5

Literature comparison of diameter of fine particles.

Source	Cell type	Abuse	Size distribution	GMMD
This study test 1	NMC	Heat	Cascade impactor	466 nm
This study test 2	NCA	Heat	Cascade impactor	534 nm
(Premnath et al. 2022)	LFP	Nail	EEPS	79 nm
(Premnath et al. 2022)	LFP	Overcharge	EEPS	249 nm/ 230 nm
(Premnath et al. 2022)	NMC	Nail	EEPS	163 nm
(Claassen et al. 2024a)	LFP	Heat	ELPI	568 nm
(Claassen et al. 2024a)	LCO	Heat	ELPI	668 nm

3.2. Elemental composition

Tests 1 and 2 were executed using a cascade impactor. Each size fraction of the particle distribution was analyzed independently. The obtained elemental composition expressed as a percentage of the total amount of detected elements is shown in Fig. 5 for test 1, and in Fig. 5 for test 2. It should be noted that only size fractions that are relevant are included in the figures. The stages for the capture of the smallest and the biggest particles are not contained due to the small amount of captured mass of the particles. The elements C, H, and O were not measured due

to the analytical method used. However, these elements are expected to be a significant part of the particles composition. The analysis reveals a higher concentration of alkali metals (Li and Na) in smaller particles (below 500 nm). Conversely, the larger particles, with dimensions exceeding 1 μm, exhibited a higher concentration of heavy metals, with nickel proving to be the most abundant. The primary mechanism driving this compositional difference is the elemental boiling point. Alkali metals, such as Na (883 °C) and Li (1342 °C), possess boiling points lower than the peak internal temperatures of the thermal runaway. Consequently, these elements vaporize and subsequently condense to form ultrafine particles. In contrast, heavy metals like Ni and Co have significantly higher boiling points (2913 °C and 2927 °C, respectively) and are primarily ejected as coarser fragments. Furthermore, the elevated Li concentration observed in test 2 is attributed to the more aggressive reaction dynamics, which enhance the vaporization of the Li-rich electrolyte. In the majority of the samples, Pb and Cd were not detected.

In the analysis of particles captured by the cascade impactor, the stages with below-limit particles were excluded from the evaluation. To verify that this procedure did not lead to a significant mistake in the results, additional tests were performed. Tests 3 and 4 involved the use of a single polycarbonate filter to capture particles of varying sizes. These particles were subsequently subjected to elemental analysis. The obtained results are presented in Fig. 5 in absolute values in relation to the mass of the particles.

The elemental composition of test 3 (Fig. 5c) shows the presence of Ni and Li, with Ni accounting for 19.0% and Li for 10.4% of the total mass. Elements that account for more than 0.5% of the total composition

Fig. 5. Elemental composition of particles expressed in absolute portions of the mass from (a) battery cell No.1 and (b) battery cell No.2.

include Al, Cu, Co, and Mn. Additionally, Na, Fe, Cd, Cr, and Pb were identified. The particles from test 4, as shown in Fig. 5d, exhibited Ni and Li concentrations of 28.9% and 17.6%, respectively. Battery cell No. 2 exhibited a higher concentration of Li compared to battery cell No. 1. This difference may be attributed to the more advanced oxidation state of battery cell No. 1, which likely resulted in a higher proportion of undetected elements. Other descended amount of detected elements are Al, Cu, Co, Na, Mn, and Fe. Furthermore, trace elements were detected only in negligible concentrations, specifically Cr, Pb, and Cd at 0.0009%, 0.0009%, and 0.007% for test 3, and 0.0001%, 0.001%, and 0.004% for test 4, respectively.

These compositional results establish a clear and recurring trend: the elemental partitioning during thermal runaway is highly size-dependent. The data confirm that the physical vaporization of low-boiling-point elements (Li) consistently drives the formation of submicron aerosols, while mechanical fragmentation of refractory elements (Ni) dominates the fraction larger than 1 μm .

3.3. Morphology

The morphology of the collected particles was investigated using SEM. The particles utilized for tests 5 and 6 were once again captured through the use of a cascade impactor. The duration of this process was 15 s, with an airflow rate of 10 liters per minute, ensuring the formation of a thin layer of particles on the aluminum foils. The SEM images from tests 5 and 6 are displayed in Fig. 6. These images offer insights into the morphology of the particles and the structure of the agglomerates that formed. For the analysis, stages 6 and 14 were utilized. Stage 6 exhibited a size range of 94 nm to 152 nm. Stage 14 ranged from 3.62 μm to 5.32 μm .

It is evident that each stage of the impactor collects particles with distinct morphologies, indicative of the alterations in chemical composition, as illustrated in Fig. 6. Particles measuring below 1000 nm exhibited higher lithium (Li) content, while larger particles contained higher heavy metal content. The images obtained from stage 14 reveal a non-uniform distribution of particles, with smooth spherical particles

Fig. 6. SEM images of particles collected on foils by cascade impactor a) stage 14 battery cell No.2; b) stage 14, battery cell No.2; c) stage 6, battery cell No.2; d) stage 6, battery cell No.2.

being juxtaposed against rough surfaces. The smooth spheres form via localized melting of specific metallic components (Cu, Fe) during peak temperatures, followed by rapid quenching upon ejection. Conversely, the rough, irregular particles originate from the mechanical fragmentation of non-melted materials. Furthermore, particles from the sixth stage demonstrated a propensity for agglomeration, resulting in the formation of plate-like structures. In comparison, the composition of stage-6 particles exhibits greater uniformity than that of stage-14 particles. The primary finding derived from Fig. 6 is the morphological confirmation of two distinct particle generation mechanisms: the sub-micron agglomerates are formed via the condensation of vaporized elements, whereas the coarser particles ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$), irregular particles are generated through the mechanical fragmentation and ejection of solid cell components.

The particles that were captured during test 6 to stage 14 were also used for EDS mapping of elemental composition. The SEM images, accompanied by the corresponding elemental mapping, are presented in

Fig. 7. This qualitative mapping visualizes elemental distribution across distinct particle morphologies, complementing the preceding quantitative data. The distribution of cobalt within the image is evident, indicating its presence across a diverse range of particles as cobalt is spread throughout the original cathode material. Iron and copper appeared as spherical particles. It is assumed that these formed by melting of the anode foil for copper and the steel casing for iron, which produced droplets that later solidified during condensation. Nickel, exhibiting the highest elemental concentration, was distributed across a broad spectrum of particles which corresponds to its high content and widespread distribution. Aluminum, serving as the foil material, results in the detected part of the image passing through the particles. Therefore, its appearance in particles is limited. It is important to note that the color range was automatically scaled for each element. Consequently, individual images cannot be compared among themselves in an absolute sense.

The use of EDS was further employed to determine of the elemental

Fig. 7. EDS mapping of particles collected on foils by cascade impactor from stage 14, battery cell No.2.

composition of a specific point on a particle, as illustrated in Fig. 7. The size of the particle in question was approximately 10 μm. The particle's formation was attributed to a coagulation process, resulting in its larger size compared to other particles. The EDS analysis revealed that the predominant element is nickel, with a percentage of 56.4%, which aligns with the results obtained through AAS which is 64.5%. The elements with the next highest detection rates were carbon, cobalt, and aluminum, with compositions of 13.1%, 10.4%, and 10.3%, respectively. Aluminum content is expected to be overestimated since the analysis was conducted on an aluminum foil potentially increasing its concentration. AAS analysis showed cobalt and aluminum content 9.3% and 2.8% respectively. An additional comparison of elements such as manganese, iron, and copper shows a similar trend, with AAS detecting 0.2% Mn, 1.3% Fe, and 4.9% Cu, while EDS analysis revealed 0.1% Mn, 0.6% Fe, and 0.8% Cu. These differences are attributed to the inherent limitations of SEM-EDS in quantifying trace elements. A comprehensive overview of all detected elements and their respective concentrations is provided in Table 6.

Overall, the morphological evidence corroborates the elemental findings. The presence of smooth, spherical larger particles (> 1 μm), confirms localized melting and rapid quenching of specific metallic components, while the highly uniform, plate-like agglomerates in the

Table 6
Elemental composition of a single particle pointed by a green cross in Fig. 7 from the EDS spectrum.

Element	C	O	F	Al	Si	P	S	Cl
[wt%]	13,1	1,5	0,5	10,3	4,1	1,3	0,3	0,1
Element	K	Ca	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
[wt%]	0,1	0,2	0,1	0,6	10,4	56,4	0,8	0,2

submicron range are characteristic of condensation processes from vaporized elements.

4. Conclusions

This study characterized the size distribution, elemental composition, and morphology of aerosol particles emitted during the thermal runaway of 18650 cylindrical lithium-ion batteries. While these cylindrical cells provide critical baseline insights, their specific high-velocity venting dynamics may differ from pouch or prismatic formats. To accurately assess these emissions, the aerosols were systematically collected and fractionated using a cascade impactor alongside single filters. This comprehensive methodology reveals the fundamental formation mechanisms of hazardous battery aerosols.

- Gravimetric analysis revealed a critical dependence of particle size distribution on cathode chemistry. NMC cells exhibited a unimodal distribution peaking in the submicron range (252–377 nm). In contrast, the more reactive NCA chemistry produced a bimodal profile (peaks at 152–252 nm and 0.94–1.62 μm), driven by its lower thermal stability and the subsequent violent mechanical ejection of coarser fragments during venting.
- Elemental distribution is strictly size-dependent and governed by thermodynamic boiling points. Volatile alkali metals (Li, Na) vaporize during peak TR temperatures and subsequently nucleate into ultrafine particles (< 500 nm). Conversely, heavy metals (Ni, Co) with high boiling points do not vaporize; they are predominantly ejected as larger (> 1 μm) solid or molten fragments.
- Particle morphology strongly correlates with chemical composition and formation pathways. Submicron particles exhibit uniform

composition and tend to agglomerate into plate-like structures. Coarser fractions display extreme heterogeneity, containing a mix of rough, irregular fragments with smooth spheres (e.g., Cu, Fe), which indicate localized melting and rapid quenching.

- The emission profiles directly reflect the pristine cell composition, releasing substantial quantities of deeply respirable, hazardous heavy metals (Ni, Co, Cu) and lithium. While highly toxic trace metals (Pb, Cd) were largely undetected in fractionated samples, their occasional presence on single filters indicates risk of trace contamination.

While this study reveals the fundamental size-dependent vaporization mechanism of battery aerosols, several limitations must be acknowledged. Although the highly stochastic nature of thermal runaway inherently limits the exact quantitative repeatability of total aerosol mass emissions, the fundamental size-dependent elemental partitioning is driven by invariant thermodynamic properties, making this core mechanism generalizable even with a limited sample size per experimental setup. The current findings are specifically bound to the tested cylindrical cell formats and the semi-quantitative limits of SEM-EDS analysis.

Hazardous submicron aerosol emission is a universal feature of Li-ion battery cell thermal runaway. These findings are critical for accurately assessing the acute health hazards associated with battery fires and for driving the development of advanced safety measures to reduce these emissions at the source. Given the prevalence of these deeply respirable, toxic particles, immediate mitigation strategies are imperative. The mandatory use of Self-Contained Breathing Apparatus for first responders and the integration of robust HEPA filtration in indoor EV and battery storage facilities are essential to prevent deep-lung deposition and occupational exposure.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Simona Šachrová: Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Lukáš Preisler:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Renata Komendová:** Supervision. **Tomáš Sitek:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jiří Pospíšil:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research and by Brno University of Technology in the frame of Specific Research Fund No. FCH/FSI-J–23–8269. We acknowledge CzechNanoLab Research Infrastructure supported by MEYS CR (LM2023051).

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

Ahlatwaj, A., Wiedensohler, A., Mishra, S.K., 2020. An Overview on the role of relative humidity in airborne transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in indoor environments. *Aerosol Air Qual. Res.* 20, 1856–1861. <https://doi.org/10.4209/aaqr.2020.06.0302>.
 Alves, C.A., Vicente, A.M.P., Calvo, A.I., Baumgardner, D., Amato, F., Querol, X., Pio, C., Gustafsson, M., 2020. Physical and chemical properties of non-exhaust particles

generated from wear between pavements and tyres (1994). *Atmos. Environ.* 224, 117252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2019.117252>.
 Barone, T.L., Dubaniewicz, T.H., Friend, S.A., Zlochower, I.A., Bugarski, A.D., Rayyan, N. S., 2021. Lithium-ion battery explosion aerosols: Morphology and elemental composition. *Aerosol Sci. Technol.* 55, 1183–1201. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02786826.2021.1938966>.
 Chen, S., Wang, Z., Yan, W., 2020. Identification and characteristic analysis of powder ejected from a lithium ion battery during thermal runaway at elevated temperatures, 123169–123169. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.123169>.
 Claassen, M., Bingham, B., Chow, J.C., Watson, J.G., Wang, Y., Wang, X., 2024b. Characterization of Lithium-Ion Battery Fire Emissions—Part 1: Chemical Composition of Fine Particles (PM2.5). *Batter. (Basel)* 10, 301. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries10090301>.
 Claassen, M., Bingham, B., Chow, J.C., Watson, J.G., Chu, P., Wang, Y., Wang, X., 2024a. Characterization of Lithium-Ion Battery Fire Emissions—Part 2: Particle Size Distributions and Emission Factors. *Batter. (Basel)* 10, 366. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries10100366>.
 Einstein, A., 1905. Über die von der molekularkinetischen Theorie der Wärme geforderte Bewegung von in ruhenden Flüssigkeiten suspendierten Teilchen. *Ann. der Phys.* 322, 549–560. <https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.19053220806>.
 Essl, C., Golubkov, A.W., Gasser, E., Nachtnebel, M., Zankel, A., Ewert, E., Fuchs, A., 2020. Comprehensive hazard analysis of failing automotive lithium-ion batteries in overtemperature experiments. *Batter. (Basel)* 6, 30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries6020030>.
 Essl, C., Seifert, L., Rabe, M., Fuchs, A., 2021. Early detection of failing automotive batteries using gas sensors. *Batter. (Basel)* 7, 25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries7020025>.
 García, A., Monsalve-serrano, J., Micó, C., Guaraco-figueira, C., 2024. Detailed characterisation of particle emissions from the thermal runaway of nickel-manganese-cobalt 811 lithium-ion batteries at different states of charge. *J. Energy Storage* 96, 112695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.112695>.
 Golubkov, A.W., Fuchs, D., Wagner, J., Wiltsche, H., Stangl, C., Fauler, G., Voitic, G., Thaler, A., Hacker, V., 2014. Thermal-runaway experiments on consumer Li-ion batteries with metal-oxide and olivin-type cathodes. *RSC Adv.* 4, 3633–3642. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3ra45748f>.
 Kim, K.-hyun, Kabir, E., Kabir, S., 2015. A review on the human health impact of airborne particulate matter. *Environ. Int.* 74, 136–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2014.10.005>.
 Kulkarni, P., Baron, P.A., Willeke, K., 2011. *Aerosol measurement: principles, techniques, and applications*, Third Edition. John Wiley & Sons, Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118001684> (Third edition).
 Larsson, C.F., Mellander, B.-erik, 2014. Abuse by External Heating, Overcharge and Short Circuiting of Commercial Lithium-Ion Battery Cells. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 161, A1611. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0311410jes>.
 Larsson, F., Andersson, P., Blomqvist, P., Lorén, A., Mellander, B.-erik, 2014. Characteristics of lithium-ion batteries during fire tests. *J. Power Sources* 271, 414–420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.08.027>.
 Li, C., Wang, H., Li, Y., Lu, L., 2024b. Venting particle-induced arc of lithium-ion batteries during the thermal runaway. *ETransportation (Amst.)* 22, 100350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etrans.2024.100350>.
 Li, W., Xue, Y., Feng, X., Liu, J., Zhang, F., Rao, S., Zhang, T., Gao, Z., Du, Z., Ni, C., Shi, J., Wang, H., Rong, C., Wang, D., 2024a. Enhancing understanding of particle emissions from lithium-ion traction batteries during thermal runaway: An overview and challenges. *ETransportation (Amst.)* 22, 100354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etrans.2024.100354>.
 Liu, K., Wang, Y., Lai, X., 2022. *Data Science-Based Full-Lifespan Management of Lithium-Ion Battery: Manufacturing, Operation and Reutilization*. Springer Nature, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-01340-9>.
 Loveridge, M.J., Remy, G., Kourra, N., Genieser, R., Barai, A., Lain, M.J., Guo, Y., Amor-segan, M., Williams, M.A., Amietszajew, T., Ellis, M., Bhagat, R., Greenwood, D., 2018. Looking deeper into the galaxy (Note 7). *Batter. (Basel)* 4, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries4010003>.
 Luo, H., Wang, Y., Feng, Y.H., Fan, X.Y., Han, X., Wang, P.F., 2022. Lithium-Ion Batteries under Low-Temperature Environment: Challenges and Prospects. *Materials* 15, 8166. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15228166>.
 Mao, N., Wang, Z.-rong, Chung, Y.-hong, Shu, C.-min, 2019. Overcharge cycling effect on the thermal behavior, structure, and material of lithium-ion batteries. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 163, 114147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2019.114147>.
 Nedjalkov, A., Meyer, J., Köhring, M., Doering, A., Angelmahr, M., Dahle, S., Sander, A., Fischer, A., Schade, W., 2016. Toxic gas emissions from damaged lithium ion batteries-analysis and safety enhancement solution. *Batter. (Basel)* 2, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries2010005>.
 Niu, H., Chen, C., Liu, Y., Li, L., Li, Z., Ji, D., Huang, X., 2022. Mitigating thermal runaway propagation of NCM 811 prismatic batteries via hollow glass microspheres plates. *Process. Saf. Environ. Prot.* 162, 672–683. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2022.04.049>.
 Pfrang, A., Kriston, A., Ruiz, V., Lebedeva, N., di Persio, F., 2017. Safety of rechargeable energy storage systems with a focus on Li-ion technology. In: *Emerging Nanotechnologies In Rechargeable Energy Storage Systems*. Elsevier, Boston, MA, pp. 253–290.
 Premnath, V., Wang, Y., Wright, N., Khalek, I., Uribe, S., 2022. Detailed characterization of particle emissions from battery fires. *Aerosol Sci. Technol.* 56, 337–354. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02786826.2021.2018399>.
 Sall, M.L., Diaw, A.K.D., Gningue-sall, D., Efreanova Aaron, S., Aaron, J.-jacques, 2020. Toxic heavy metals: impact on the environment and human health, and treatment

- with conducting organic polymers, a review. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res. Int.* 27, 29927–29942. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-09354-3>.
- Spotnitz, R., Franklin, J., 2003. Abuse behavior of high-power, lithium-ion cells. *J. Power Sources* 113, 81–100. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(02\)00488-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(02)00488-3).
- Ubaldi, S., Conti, M., Marra, F., Russo, P., 2023. Identification of Key Events and Emissions during Thermal Abuse Testing on NCA 18650 Cells. *Energ. (Basel)* 16, 3250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16073250>.
- Valavanidis, A., Fiotakis, K., Vlachogianni, T., 2008. Airborne Particulate Matter and Human Health: Toxicological Assessment and Importance of Size and Composition of Particles for Oxidative Damage and Carcinogenic Mechanisms. *J. Environ. Sci. Health Part. C. Environ. Carcinog. & Ecotoxicol. Rev.* 26, 339–362. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10590500802494538>.
- Wang, G., Kong, D., Ping, P., Wen, J., He, X., Zhao, H., He, X., Peng, R., Zhang, Y., Dai, X., 2023a. Revealing particle venting of lithium-ion batteries during thermal runaway: A multi-scale model toward multiphase process. *ETransportation (Amst.)* 16, 100237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etrans.2023.100237>.
- Wang, H., Zhang, Y., Li, W., Li, C., Ouyang, M., 2020. Particles Released by Abused Prismatic Ni-rich Automotive Lithium-ion Batteries. *WSEAS Trans. Syst. CONTROL* 15, 30–38.
- Wang, H., Wang, Q., Jin, C., Xu, C., Zhao, Y., Li, Y., Zhong, C., Feng, X., 2023b. Detailed characterization of particle emissions due to thermal failure of batteries with different cathodes, 131646-131646 *J. Hazard. Mater.* 458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.131646>.
- Xu, Y., Wang, Y., Chen, D., 2024. Soot formation and its hazards in battery thermal runaway. *J. Aerosol Sci.* 181, 106420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaerosci.2024.106420>.
- Zhang, Y., Wang, H., Li, W., Li, C., 2019a. Quantitative identification of emissions from abused prismatic Ni-rich lithium-ion batteries. *ETRANSPORTATION* 2, 100031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etrans.2019.100031>.
- Zhang, Y., Wang, H., Li, W., Li, C., Ouyang, M., 2019b. Size distribution and elemental composition of vent particles from abused prismatic Ni-rich automotive lithium-ion batteries. *J. Energy Storage* 26, 100991. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2019.100991>.
- Zhu, M., Zhang, S., Chen, Y., Zhao, L., Chen, M., 2023. Experimental and analytical investigation on the thermal runaway propagation characteristics of lithium-ion battery module with NCM pouch cells under various state of charge and spacing. *J. Energy Storage* 72, 108380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.108380>.